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Participation in Voting Parties Based on Gender and Ages

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Abstract

In a democracy, a general election is a platform for citizens to use their political rights. However, not all citizens use it well, leading to an imperfect voting participation level. This situation motivates this study to exist. With this intention, this paper examines and analyzes the participation to vote decision in the party general election in 2019 based on gender and ages. Backing up this goal, we use the people in three regencies in West Java: Subang, Majalengka, and Sumedang, as the population. Because of these areas, we utilize multistage random sampling to take 600 people as the samples. As the statistical checking, we use the Mann-Whitney U and Kruskal-Wallis to test the hypotheses based on the categorical responses. After investigating the answers through the statistical test and discussing their outputs, we deduce that the participation of females is lower than that of males, demonstrating the gender gap. Also, the younger the participants, the higher involvement to vote.

Keywords: Ages, Gender, General Election, Participation in the Vote

1. Introduction

As a science, marketing can be applied in several fields, like business and politics (Bastian, 2010). In business, marketing functions to perceive and exchange value through communication with consumers. Similarly, political communication is needed when the parties intend to deliver value to their voters via campaign (Korschum, Martik, Vadakkepatt, 2020). Furthermore, marketing in the company persuades consumers to purchase goods or utilize services (Aribowo, Sucherly, Suryana, & Effendi, 2016). Meanwhile, the marketing in politics focuses on attracting voters to choose the majors (Lestari & Rafni, 2018), the regents (Solihah, Bainus, & Rahmatunnisa, 2015), the governors (William & Wuryandari, 2020), the president (Fowler, Ridout, & Franz, 2016), and the parties (Aribowo et al., 2016).

In the democratic system, the victorious general election depends on the participation rate of citizens: the higher this rate, the more qualified the democracy (Mulyadi, 2019). Moreover, Hasan et al. (2021) explain that accumulated voices are helpful for the head and vice candidates of regency, municipality, and state leaders to achieve their position. Additionally, for parties, Adam, Bataubun, and Jalal (2021) enlighten that a party can place its representatives in the parliament if these voices exceed the established parliamentary threshold. In this situation, the general election commission must set and announce the eligible vote calculation result (Noor, 2009).

Nationally, the participation level of citizens in Indonesia since multi parties in 1999 tends to go down from 92.7% this year to 81.7% in 2019 (see Table 1). It means the political rights to choose the parties are not performed well. According to Aribowo et al. (2016), this evidence is due to several reasons: (1) elections do not contribute to the welfare of society, (2) lousy performance of political parties in front of the public, the parties only pay attention to group interest, (3) dishonesty and immoral of politicians, reflected by their corruption, and (4) parties do not realize their promise to their supporters, (5) bias exists to execute the public election.

Table 1: The number of parties, the participation rate, and abstain level of Indonesians in the general election between 1999 and 2019

Year	Total			Participation rate	Abstain rate
	All parties	National parties	Local parties in Aceh		
1999	48	48	-	92.6%	7.4%
2004	24	24	-	84.1%	15.9%
2009	44	38	6	70.9%	29.1%
2014	15	12	3	75.1%	24.9%
2019	20	16	4	81.7%	18.3%

Notes: In 2009 and 2004, the national parties existed. After 2004, local parties from Aceh appeared. Six, three, and four local parties were available from 44, 15, and 20 participating parties in the general election between 2009 and 2019. The rest were from the national (see the public election supervisory agency information in 2019 in Manado city). The participation and abstain rates between 1999 and 2014 and in 2019 refer to Damarjati (2019) and Jelita (2019), respectively.

Source: The General Election Supervisory Agency of Manado city (2019), Damarjati (2019), and Jelita (2019)

Through the literature study, Willocq (2019) emphasizes that gender and age can affect the voting decision besides the other determinants. Unlike Willocq (2019) with a theoretical perspective, Bibi (2020) points out the low participation for females in the general election in Pakistan. When studying the voting behavior around 13 countries in East and Southeast Asia, Liu (2020) reports the gender gap in voting turnout in Malaysia: participation of women is lower than that of men. However, contrary results based on this determinant exist, as displayed by Wagner, Johann, and Kritzingner (2012), Aribowo et al. (2016), Lee, Park, and Kim (2016), Intyaswati, Maryani, Sugiana, and Venus (2021), demonstrating no association.

Besides, a theoretical review of Willocq (2019), the studies trying to examine the association between ages and voting decisions with empirical data are available [see Wagner et al. (2012), Aribowo et al. (2016), Liu (2020), and Intyaswati et al. (2021), for instance]. In their study, Wagner et al. (2012) verify a positive relationship between age and voting decisions. Also, Aribowo et al. (2016) document the significant relationship after employing the Chi-square test and analysis. However, Lee et al. (2016), Liu (2020), and Intyaswati et al. (2021) cannot prove this relationship.

Women have less political knowledge than men (Dassonneville, Nugent, Hooghe, & Lau, 2020). Besides, they perceive that politics is dishonest, brutal, and complicated (Zamroni, 2013). Therefore, they apathetically vote (Willocq, 2019). This circumstance is supported by Bibi (2020), presenting a small turnout of Pakistani females. In her study learning gender gap in voting turnout, around 13 countries in East and Southeast Asia, Liu (2020) reports that a negative gender gap only exists in Malaysia, with females as the reference category. It means the participation of women is significantly less than that of men. Based on this information, this study proposes hypothesis one like this.

H₁: Unlike men, women have less participation in voting.

The minimum age to participate in the general election is dissimilar among the countries. For example, the intended age in Austria is 16 (Wagner et al., 2012), Indonesia is 17 (Intyaswati et al., 2021). According to the Indonesian Health Ministry age categories published in 2009 cited by Al-Amin and Juniati (2017), the seventeenth is the bottom level of adolescence, and 25 is the top. Furthermore, the adult and elderly are aged 26 to 45 and 46 to 65. According to Willocq (2019), mature adults have a favorite party to be chosen and stable philosophy in their mind;

therefore, they tend to participate more in the general election. Wagner et al. (2012) confirm this positive tendency in their study: Austrian voting quality above 31 is higher than the persons between 18 to 30. Based on this information, this study proposes hypothesis two like this.

H₂: The older participant, the greater participation in voting.

2. Method

2.1. Variable Definition

This study utilizes three categorical variables: gender, age, and voting participation, mentioning the proposed hypotheses.

- a. To measure gender, we use two categorical variables: male and female.
- b. To measure age, we use the variable with three categories: teenagers, adults, and elderly, aged between 17 and 25, 26 and 45, 46 and 65, respectively.
- c. To measure participation in the voting parties, we mention Aribowo et al. (2015) by categorizing three options of the answer: (1) always, (2) seldom, and (3) never.

2.2. Population, Samples, and Sampling Method

The total population of this study is 2,896,989 voters at the three regencies in West Java: Subang, Majalengka, and Sumedang, where this information comes from the local general election commission. Moreover, the total minimum samples refer to the online calculator at www.calculator.net/sample-size-calculator.html utilizing a 95% confidence level, a 5% error margin, 50% population proportion. Based on this calculation, the minimum sample size is 385. Additionally, we add the samples to 600 respondents to get a more accurate measurement.

Table 2: The allocation of samples based on population

Regency	Total population	Proportion	Total Sample
Subang	1,110,185	38.32%	230 (rounded)
Majalengka	952,528	32.88%	197 (rounded)
Sumedang	834,276	28.80%	173 (rounded)
Total	2.896,989	100%	600

Source: Researchers' database

Because of the three regencies, we employ a multistage random sampling method to take 600 people as the samples based on population proportion (see Table 2). This sampling method demands two or more steps of random sampling based on the area of the population. After that, the people in this area are randomly chosen (Sedgwick, 2015). Based on this context, firstly, this study takes 27 districts as the sample area from 82 existing districts in three regencies as population area. Then, 74 villages distributed in the 27 districts are selected as the sub-sample area. Furthermore, 230, 197, and 173 people are taken randomly based on the total villagers in 74 districts.

2.3. Method to test the responses

This study utilizes categorical variables. Hence, according to Hartono (2012), this circumstance requires non-parametric statistical testing.

- a. Since gender has two categories, we use the Mann-Whitney test to compare the participating tendency difference, as Santoso (2005) explains.
- b. Since ages have three categories, we employ the Kruskal Wallis test to compare the participating tendency difference, as Santoso (2005) describes.

2.4. Method to collect the data

This study utilizes a survey to grab respondents' answers (Hartono, 2012). To make respondents rapidly respond, we use closed questions with some choices related to the variables, as Sugiyono (2017) suggests. In this context, the responses needed are associated with categorical variables: participation in the voting parties, gender, and ages.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Descriptive Statistics

The data needed in this study are collected by onsite survey between September 9 and October 26, 2019. Then, these data are presented by frequency based on gender, age, and voting participation, in Table 3 exhibits. In this survey, the females and teenagers dominantly participate, shown by 52% and 59.83%, singly. For the participants with the continuous response is 94%.

Table 3: Descriptive Statistics of Gender, Age, and Voting Participation

Variable	Categorical description	N	Percentage
Gender	Male	288	48.00%
	Female	312	52.00%
Age	Teenagers: 17 to 25 years old	359	59.83%
	Adults: 26 to 45 years old	119	19.83%
	Elderly: 46 to 65 years old	122	20.33%
Participation to vote	Continuous	564	94.00%
	Seldom	10	1.67%
	Never	26	4.33%

Source: Output of IBM SPSS 19

3.2. The output of the statistical examination

Table 4 is the Mann-Whitney U testing result for the first hypothesis. It displays that the mean rank of females, 293.90, is lower than that of males, 307.65, with the asymptotic probability (1-tailed) for Z-statistic of 0.009. Because this value is lower than the significance level of 5% and the mean rank of women is below that of men, we accept the first hypothesis: the participation of women to vote is less than that of men.

Table 4: The test result of Mann-Whitney

Gender	Mean Rank	Description	Participation to vote
Male	307.65	Mann-Whitney U	42870.000
Female	293.90	Z-statistic	-2.358
		Asymptotic probability (1-tailed)	0.009

Source: Modified output of IBM SPSS 19

Table 5 is the Kruskal Wallis testing result for the second hypothesis. It demonstrates that teenagers, adults, and elderly mean ranks are 310.94, 287.46, and 282.65, respectively, supported by the asymptotic probability for Chi-Square of 0.000. Because this value is lower than the significance level of 5%, we reject the second hypothesis. Instead, we find a negative relationship between age and mean rank: the more senior participants, the less voting tendency.

Table 5: The test result of Kruskal Wallis

Group of age	Mean Rank	Description	Participation to vote
Teenagers: 17-25	310.94	Chi-Square	19.436
Adults: 26-45	287.46	Degree of freedom	2
Elderly: 46-65	282.65	Asymptotic probability	0.000

Source: Modified output of IBM SPSS 19

3.3. Discussion

From the first hypothesis testing result, we find that women have less participation in voting than men, reflecting a gender gap. Women assume that politics is filthy; therefore, they avoid being involved inside. They know many cases, i.e., bribery and corruption, happen after the legislative members representing their party are on duty by watching and reading news on television and the online media on their smartphone. Therefore, this fact aligns with the research of Bibi (2020) and Liu (2020), exhibiting women tend to have less voting participation.

The second hypothesis testing result shows that the younger, the greater voting involvement. The increase in this participation cannot be separated from political education in advance by the general election commission. Fundamentally, the young generation is idealist actors and critical thinkers. Therefore, this generation can easily vote as long as the material contents support them better to be respectable citizens. Thus, this fact contradicts the study of Wagner et al. (2012), declaring the more senior, the higher the voting decision.

Regarding the gender gap explaining that women dislike bad politics, the parliament members must avoid corruption and bribery. Furthermore, to eliminate this gap, they must become good examples for people by showing integrity and excellence to work, demonstrating attention, and providing solutions to social problems. Besides, the younger the voters, the more tendency to participate in general elections indicates effective political education in these regencies: Subang, Majalengka, and Sumedang. Therefore, educating teenagers to vote in these areas needs to be followed by the other regencies and municipalities in Indonesia.

4. Conclusion

This research intends to examine and analyze the difference in participation to vote parties based on gender and age. By employing the 600 citizens from three regencies, Subang, Majalengka, and Sumedang, as the samples through survey from September 9 to October 26, 2019, this study infers that female involvement in voting is inferior to that of males. Besides, the voting contribution is influenced by ages: the voting participation of the youth is higher than that of the adults and the elderly.

Although efficaciously proving the difference in voting participation based on gender and age, this research is still limited in the modeling aspect. Therefore, the following scientists are expected to explain voting participation determinants, such as social media marketing, political trust, satisfaction with democracy, political awareness, internal and external political efficacy, political talk. Furthermore, the structural equation model can be applied to analyze data and examine the relationship declared in the hypothesis statistically.

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